

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL

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ABSTRACT

The organization of harmoniously developed personality has always been an important requirement and the main goal of society. This article discusses the content of cultivating the creative abilities of preschool children, and developing their intellectual potential.

The organization of the harmonious development of the individual has always been an important requirement and the main goal of society. Today, one of the most important tasks is to bring up preschool children as a comprehensively developed, physically healthy, mentally mature and spiritually formed generation. One of the most important tasks for educators in preschool education is to cultivate children's creativity and creativity, as well as the rational use of natural resources. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated September 30, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system" and "On the organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan A new system has been created in this area in accordance with the resolution of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan. Under this system, the development and implementation of a unified state policy in

the field of preschool education, the expansion of the state and non-governmental network of preschool education and strengthening the material and technical base, providing them with qualified teachers, preschool education The tasks are set to dramatically increase the coverage of children, the comprehensive intellectual, spiritual-aesthetic, physical development of children through the introduction of modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process, to radically improve the quality of their preparation for school. At all stages of the development of society, the human heart from an early age is characterized by such qualities as goodness, nobility, humanity, humanity, intelligence, morality, diligence, patriotism, honesty, purity, eloquence, kindness, knowledge. enrichment has been the norm of human maturity. Because a perfect person has a high level of spirituality. A person with a high level of spirituality knows and follows

the history, customs, values, traditions and culture of his people.

Preschool is a time when a child has a strong desire to grow, develop, express himself, learn, and learn. It is during this period that the foundation is laid for the development of the child's human qualities and mental potential. The earlier education begins with a preschooler, the earlier the results will be seen and the more positive the child's life will be. Therefore, the development of children's thinking becomes one of the main tasks. Preschool is a very important part of a child's development. During this period, the child's physical, moral, psychological health is formed and mental development skills are improved. Parents who want their children to be successful, smart and talented in the future should pay attention to their development from this time.

The intellectual development of preschool children is very important as they begin to develop skills to successfully master educational activities. The collection of information for preschool age is accelerating, cognitive processes are improving, speech is being formed. School children with advanced intelligence are quicker to learn and memorize new material, more confident in their abilities, and more willing to learn as practice shows. A special place in the development of the intellectual abilities of educators of preschool education includes children's didactic games, which are a means of teaching and help children to acquire and strengthen their knowledge, as well as help them to learn methods of cognitive activity. School children learn to classify, compare, and generalize due to the growing didactic

play of children's interest in educational activities. The mental development of young children should not only help to acquire and strengthen knowledge, but also to activate the thinking activities of preschool children. In this case, the educator should use a number of interactive methods and exercises. Exercises aimed at developing the intellectual abilities of preschool children include:

Draw a story or narrative through pictures. The child is shown 4 pictures, which depict a fairy tale or events known to him. The child's task is to arrange the pictures in the correct sequence and create a short story using illustrations.

Recognize objects for a number of reasons. This is called an epithet to the child, you need to determine what topic you are talking about. For example, yellow, sour, oval (lemon). Comparing two or more things. The child is invited to say what the words sound like. For example, cat, book, tom. You can tell the child how to name a cat and a dog, a table and a chair. Next, you need to find the differences in the objects: the pen and pencil, the tree and the bush.

It should be noted that in cultivating a sense of creativity in preschool children, their creativity, creativity, positive skills do not mean only school education and test scores. In English, these are called personality skills. We also know them as "human nature" or "action". A distinctive feature of the organization of children's intellectual development is the creation of positive feelings and positive emotions from new knowledge, achievements and successes. requires the appropriate use of capacity building techniques.

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